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Protecting and Projecting the Values of the EU through Trade Instruments

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1. Introduction

The values of the European Union set out in Article 2 TEU constitute the axiological reference point of the EU and, as such, have gradually acquired binding force¹. While these values are primarily promoted and protected within the Union itself through various mechanisms such as those provided for in Article 7 TEU or in the Regulation on budgetary conditionality, there is an increasingly urgent need to affirm and guarantee these values in the Union's relations with third countries.

The main reason for this is that these values are not seen as societal choices specific to Europe: rather, they address universal concerns. The premise is therefore that humanity as a whole should be able to benefit from them, if only because it is the victim of the violations committed against them. This approach is enshrined in Article 3(5) of the TEU, which states that "in its relations with the wider world, the Union shall uphold and promote its values". It may be illustrated by reference to the restrictive measures adopted against Niger, which are intended to counteract breaches of democracy, the rule of law, and serious violations of Human Rights, all of which represent values of the Union². At the same time, the gradual introduction of environmental protection (which is not, however, mentioned in Article 2 TEU), particularly through the protection of Human Rights, is a movement that has begun but deserves to be strengthened³.

This Policy Brief reflects on the ways in which the EU can use the instruments of trade policy to promote its fundamental values. This ambition is reflected in a twofold movement, where the EU acts both internally, to *protect* its values against outside pressures, and externally, to *project* these values, drawing on the economic power of the European market. The Policy Brief outlines the existing tools the EU can use to protect and project its values (Section 2). Next the prospects for strengthening this strategy, based on the potential expansion of EU values to include sustainable development, are outlined (Section 3). Finally, there is a brief conclusion (Section 4).

2. Existing Tools for Protecting Values within the Union and Projecting Values Beyond the Union.

A) Instruments for protecting values

Instruments aimed at protecting the values of the Union are part of a two-pronged approach of prevention and, where necessary, response to external threats.

The Anti-Coercion Regulation adopted in November 2023⁴ is a first example of general legislation aimed at protecting the Union's values. More specifically, it is intended to respond to foreign interference of an economic nature

¹ See Judgment of the Court (Grand Chamber) of 20 April 2021, *Repubblika v Il-Prim Ministru*, Case C-896/19, paragraphs 63-64.

² See Recital 8 and Article 2 § 1(c) & (d) of the Council Decision (CFSP) 2023/2287 of 23 October 2023 concerning restrictive measures in view of the situation in Niger.

³ See Judgment of the Court (Grand Chamber) of 25 June 2020, *A and Others (Wind turbines at Aalter*

and Nevele), Case C-24/19, paragraphs 45-47 ; Judgement of the Court (Grand Chamber) of 25 June 2024, *Ilva and Others*, Case C-626/22, paragraphs 71-72.

⁴ See Regulation (EU) 2023/2675 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 November 2023 on the protection of the Union and its Member States against economic coercion by third countries, 2023/2675, 7.12.2023.

that affects the Union's freedom of choice in establishing its policies, including when it implements its values⁵. Coercion is understood as "the act of a country deploying measures, such as trade or investment restrictions, to compel another country to take an action or refrain from an action that it is not required to take under international law and that falls within its sovereignty". Thus, once such an act attributable to a third country has been established, the Commission is able to respond by adopting countermeasures which may take the form of new or increased customs duties, restrictions on the import or export of goods, restrictions on trade in services, or measures affecting access to foreign direct investment in the Union. This regulation also has undeniable symbolic value in that its mere existence is intended to deter any attempt at external pressure.

In addition to economic pressures, the EU also aims to prevent and respond to cyberattacks. This commitment has resulted in the adoption of **a directive on measures to ensure a high common level of cybersecurity across the EU**⁶. Although values are not expressly mentioned in the provisions of the directive, it is in line with the Communication "Shaping Europe's digital future,"⁷ in which the Commission called for the adoption of regulations to adapt democracy to the challenges of the digital age, including cyber threats that could undermine electoral processes. Thus, when transposing this directive, Member

States will have to put in place policies focusing on cybersecurity in the supply chain for information and communication technology (ICT) products and services, and on the inclusion and specification of cybersecurity requirements for ICT products and services in public procurement.

In the same vein, and more specifically, the EU has adopted restrictive measures to ban certain Russian media outlets within the EU in order to combat propaganda during election periods that could ultimately affect the democratic process. These measures target various channels of *Russia Today* and *Sputnik*, among others.⁸

Finally, a specific framework for **screening foreign direct investment** has also been adopted, again with a view to protecting the values of the Union⁹. The relevant Regulation provides for a procedure for assessing investments that could lead to their prohibition on the basis of the risks they pose to security or public order. Among the factors to be analysed, Member States must take into account, in particular, the effects that such investments could have on media freedom and pluralism or on access to sensitive information, including personal data, or the ability to control such information. Moreover, if the foreign investor is directly or indirectly controlled by the government, including public bodies, of a third country, this must also be taken into account.

⁵ See points 1, 2 and 7 of the preamble of Regulation (EU) 2023/2675.

⁶ Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures to ensure a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, OJ L 333, 27.12.2022.

⁷ COM/2020/67 final.

⁸ Council Regulation (EU) 2022/350 of 1 March 2022 amending Regulation (EU) No 833/2014 concerning restrictive measures in view of Russia's actions destabilising the situation in Ukraine, OJ L 65, 2.3.2022.

⁹ Regulation (EU) 2019/452 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 March 2019 establishing a framework for screening investments into the Union, OJ L 79I, 21.3.2019.

B) Instruments for projecting values

In addition to these mechanisms for protecting values, the Union has also adopted mechanisms for projecting these values.

The most representative instrument for projecting values appears to be the **Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CS3D)**¹⁰. This directive requires large European companies to prevent, detect and remedy human rights and environmental abuses throughout their global value chains – i.e., all the actors and activities involved in bringing a product to market. It thus enshrines fundamental rights as a criterion for compliance, based on Article 2 TEU. Companies must therefore ensure that their suppliers, even those outside the EU, respect workers' rights, prohibit child labour and limit their environmental impact, thereby giving concrete expression to European values. In other words, by implementing such policies, the stated aim is to impose certain standards in line with EU values on economic operators in third countries¹¹. However, the initial ambitions have been scaled back in the "Omnibus Directive", which

aims to simplify the original directive¹². For example, the duty of care would no longer apply to indirect suppliers of companies subject to the directive. The activities of the latter will only be analysed if there is plausible information to believe that they could have a negative impact on the objectives pursued by the directive.

This duty of care also applies to more specific sectors such as the import of minerals or metals from conflict-affected or high-risk areas¹³, batteries and battery waste, which imposes certain obligations with regard to workers' rights¹⁴, and certain commodities and products associated with deforestation and forest degradation, including with regard to Human Rights¹⁵.

In addition to these due diligence obligations, the Union has taken more radical steps by adopting regulations prohibiting trade in certain products due to their manufacturing methods, which could undermine the values of Article 2 TEU and, more specifically, fundamental rights. Economic operators are therefore prohibited from placing products on the Union market or making them available on the Union market if they are produced using forced labour¹⁶. At the same

¹⁰ Directive (EU) 2024/1760 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 on the sustainability due diligence obligations of undertakings and amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937 and Regulation (EU) 2023/2859, OJ L, 2024/1760, 5.7.2024.

¹¹ COM(2025) 81 final, pp. 7-8.

¹² The proposal was submitted by the European Commission on 26 February 2025, see : https://finance.ec.europa.eu/news/omnibus-package-2025-04-01_en#:~:text=On%2026%20February%202025%2C%20the,enhancing%20competitiveness%20and%20attracting%20investment.

¹³ Regulation (EU) 2017/821 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 May 2017 establishing supply chain due diligence obligations for Union importers of tin, tantalum and tungsten,

their minerals, and gold from conflict-affected and high-risk areas, OJ L 130, 19.05.2017.

¹⁴ Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2023 on batteries and battery waste, amending Directive 2008/98/EC and Regulation (EU) 2019/1020, and repealing Directive 2006/66/EC, OJ L 191, 28.7.2023.

¹⁵ Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 May 2023 on the placing on the Union market and export from the Union of certain commodities and commodity-related products linked to deforestation and forest degradation, and repealing Regulation (EU) No 995/2010, OJ L 150, 9.6.2023.

¹⁶ Regulation (EU) 2024/3015 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2024 on the prohibition of products made with forced labour on the Union market and amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937, OJ L, 2024/3015, 12.12.2024.

time, these same strictures apply to products exported from the Union. Similarly, the import of cultural goods is also subject to procedures designed to protect them from the risks of illicit trade, in particular where such trade is likely to contribute to the financing of terrorism¹⁷.

3. The Prospect of Using Trade Instruments to Promote Sustainable Development as a Union Value

The strength of the instruments described above relies above all on the economic power of the EU: it is because its partners want EU trade that they will agree to respect certain EU values¹⁸. But a delicate balance must be found between promoting values and preserving a certain economic power, which requires competitiveness and behaviour that is not always immediately compatible with those values. Most of the existing instruments have proven to be effective but some evolutions could be suggested to enhance their efficiency. As regards FDI control for example, the 4th annual report on foreign investment screening in the EU reveals that several operations have been blocked in several member States¹⁹.

There is one fundamental change that the EU could make that would have important effects on future legislative developments, from a “defensive” perspective. It could make sustainable development, including the fight

against climate change, a “value” equivalent to others. Although this would be an ambitious measure, it should be possible to amend Article 2 TEU to take this into account, especially considering the fact that sustainable development is already mentioned in Article 21 TEU.

If sustainable development were a recognized EU value, it could be further incorporated into legislative instruments. This would enable the EU to, for example, refuse the import of certain goods or services because of their environmental impact – thus definitively integrating the mode of production into the control of imported products, making it possible to control not only the finished products but also the methods of their manufacture (or provision in the case of services). This has already started with the Regulation on the prohibition of products made with forced labour but this possibility should be extended to goods produced in any way incompatible with Human Rights and Environmental protection guaranteed in the EU. This may require a double modification so that it would apply bilaterally and multilaterally, ie. both to the free trade agreements signed by the European Union and to WTO agreements, which should be updated to prevent such a requirement from being considered a trade restriction or discrimination.

¹⁷ Regulation (EU) 2019/880 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on the introduction and import of cultural goods, OJ L 151, 7.6.2019.

¹⁸ This logic is reminiscent of the “Brussels effect” theory. See Bradford A., “*The brussels effect*”, *Northwestern University Law Review*, 107(1), pp. 1-68, spec. pp. 35-39.

¹⁹ <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/be8b568f-73f3-409c-b4a4-30acfccec5283/library/a27a9d61->

[a090-4637-99e0-1d2673b7d719/details?download=true](https://www.delorscentre.eu/en/publications/detail/publication/red-lines-and-retaliation-the-eus-response-to-trumps-tariffs) . Also the anti-coercion regulation has never been used yet but is more and more referred to as a possibility to react to the new US administration tariffs policy, see for example: <https://www.delorscentre.eu/en/publications/detail/publication/red-lines-and-retaliation-the-eus-response-to-trumps-tariffs>

Furthermore, the EU could act to prohibit certain investments that are too polluting in order to move towards

a “climate veto”, which was recommended by the French committee in charge of assessment of the compatibility of CETA with the Paris Agreements.²⁰ The use of the investment screening mechanism established by Regulation 2019/452 is undoubtedly the best solution. This would involve proposing an amendment to the regulation to broaden the grounds for refusing certain investments, thereby giving national authorities the right to refuse certain investments on climate grounds. Such a possibility could also be extended to intra-EU relations to prevent restrictions on capital flows based on climate considerations from being deemed contrary to the freedoms of movement²¹.

4. Conclusion

This Policy Brief has outlined strategies for the promotion of the EU’s fundamental values through its trade policy, both internally (protecting) and externally (projecting). In addition, it has been argued that the EU could also adopt sustainable development as a value to be promoted through trade. However, these strategies could only be operational if the European Union definitively established itself as a major economic power, enabling it to impose its values on its partners (as the United States has done for a century). But the assertion of this power must be in line with the values

that the Union intends to promote. The plans to challenge the due diligence directive²² are an extremely negative signal of a desire to level down. If it were to align itself with the US approach based on deregulation, the EU would only stand to lose, as it does not have the same economic assets. Rather the EU should pursue a trade strategy that protects and projects its fundamental values, including *sustainable* development, on which it can and must base its power.

²⁰ Report of the CETA Assessment Committee, 8 September 2017, at 9.

²¹ See the Judgment of the Court (Second Chamber) of 13 July 2023, *Xella Magyarország Építőanyagipari*

Kft. v Innovációs és Technológiai Miniszter, Case C-106/22 in which Hungary’s activation of filtering was found to be contrary to the free movement of capital.

²² See *supra*, note 11.

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